

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4101689

Vidyankur XXII/1 Jan-June 2020, ISSN 2249-1503 | 41-51

Age of the Machine Human: The Choice Rests in the Hands of the Creator

Diksha Garg

St. Joseph's College of Law, Bengaluru

Abstract: Evolution is a continuous process which enabled humans to act and think in a certain manner. The cognitive evolution of man enabled him to develop tools to assist his survival. The advent of the technological progression perceived this development in form of “machine learning” and “artificial intelligence.” The paper examines the nature of artificial intelligence and its impact on the lives of humans. The paper, attempts to contemplate the difference between the humans that segregate them from AI. Overtime the lines between the two have blurred. As the machine becomes more human-like, the human began to emulate attributes of machines. There is, however, a sense of insecurity which has plagued the human due to the advent of AI, which is highlighted in the paper. Lastly, the paper identifies the role that a human plays in this “age of plasticity” and the co-dependant relation of the human-machine and the human.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Alan Turning, Age of Plasticity, Jaques Ellul, John McCarthy, Machine-Learning.

“The greatest benefit of the arrival of artificial intelligence is that AIs will help define humanity. We need AIs to tell us who we are.” – Kevin Kelly

The story of the evolution of humans can be traced back to seven million years ago when the lineage of *hominis* separated from that of the chimpanzees. The *hominis*, accommodated almost twenty different species of the *homo* genus such as the *homo erectus*, *homo neanderthalensis*, *homo habilis*, etc., some more human-like in nature than the others. However, of all species under the *homo* genus only the *Homo sapiens* have survived till date. Alongside the physical evolution of the *Homo sapiens*, we have also experienced a cognitive and social evolution.

In each stage of human evolution, man invented tools and technique to make survival easier. The evolution of these tools happened when the primary goal of human life enhanced to include power, occupation etc. instead of only focusing solely on survival. The human has many properties, but one primary factor which actually influences the human decision-making process is the concept of ‘fear’. As human evolved so did the concept of fear. If we create a timeline of the concept, we can observe that man learned to fear and demonize aspects of life that he wasn’t able to analyse and comprehend. For instance, the fear of thunder and rain which plagued the primitive man disappeared when man understood the phenomena which govern them.

While humans create technique, it would be ignorant to suggest that most of us can comprehend the magnitude of its impact. It is quite natural that those of who do not understand a technique, fear the consequences of the said technique. This aspect of a clear lack of understanding of the creation and its consequences affronts us in the

discussions and deliberations surrounding the concept of Artificial Intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence

Contrary to popular belief, the idea of artificial intelligence was conceived in the 20th century itself. The work of Alan Turing was particularly pivotal in these aspects. He was the first to have envisioned the concept of “thinking machines” in 1950. The word “artificial intelligence” on the other hand, was coined by John McCarthy in 1956, who furthered the work initiated by Turing. To actualise his thoughts and ideas, he formulated a proposal on 31st of August, 1955 as a part of the ‘Dartmouth Summer Research Project of 1956.’

The scope of artificial intelligence, as envisioned by McCarthy and Turing revolved around the concept of Machine Learning. They were highly fascinated by the idea that a machine could learn and enhance its capabilities in a manner similar to that of humans. While the proposal formulated by McCarthy and others had much to offer, they faced obvious limitations owing to the technology or rather the lack thereof. McCarthy’s work found merit with the advent of the age of computers, which not only simplified technology but essentially made it a part of our daily life.

A common man’s understanding of Artificial Intelligence stems mostly from the science fictions and the popular culture surrounding it. Any artificial intelligence is seen as an object of doom and a product of the nasty Pandora’s box. The artificial intelligence, usually projected in the form of a robot, is presented as a superhuman which would eventually be the downfall of humanity. And while an AI has the potential of being dangerous, is that all it is capable of?

To truly understand AI and the complications of drawing a limit to its impact, we must revert back to the explanations provided by McCarthy. McCarthy laid the foundation of artificial

intelligence not only on the ability of a machine to learn but also on its capacity to learn without human interference -i.e. autonomy of machines. He set the threshold as, “giving computer to do things, which when done by humans, are said to involve intelligence.”

For decades now this definition has been a source for controversy. Though McCarthy gave a cohesive definition to ‘artificial intelligence’, the terms used were as vague as they could get. There was no telling what the limit of the autonomy prescribed could be or essentially what could be categorised as “human intelligence”. However, due to the non-availability of one common definition, we can rely on the general understanding between various scientists which is that: “Artificial Intelligence, is simply the ability of a machine to learn by itself.”

Artificial Intelligence: The Semantics

The term “artificial” signifies that there is a human element involved, which creates a plethora of differences between the artificial intelligence and intelligence in itself. The machine is designed for one particular purpose, therefore the scope of its learning is limited to the purpose alone. For instance, AlphaGo and AlphaGo Zero were created specifically for the purpose of playing certain kinds of games only. The ability to work is derived from a set of algorithms’ and data which is programmed into the machine. They are programmed to not just store data but to analyse and use data to build and enhance their abilities.

AI is often seen as a culmination of data analytics and machine learning, the product of which is intelligent decision making. As specified earlier data is like the oil in the process of machine learning. Any machine learns by interpreting the underlying trend in general decision-making process. The term “intelligence” in AI refers to this

decision-making process which the machine arrives at by considering various conflicting values. In the process of developing an AI, this proves to be the most challenging stage, because it is seemingly impossible to imagine all possible outcomes of each decision that could be taken to ensure that a particular goal is achieved.

Is Artificial Intelligence Human?

Any machine whether designed to be an AI or not is constructed by a human mind but is not human. The debate to segregate an AI from a human begins here. The scientists and professors who envisioned the creation of AI wanted it to be as human-like as possible. For decades men and women strived to make the decision-making process of an AI emulating that of an ordinary, prudent human. Owing to their efforts we have now reached at a point in time where an AI can be created to imitate humans or as *Jacques Ellul* remarked the “age of plasticity”. With such a significant change in the times, new fears and new ideas emerge. The pertinent question now is that while AI is becoming more human-like by the day, can we envision a time where machines replace humans?

The answer to that question would have to be in the negative only. The main reason being that most of AI, presently being developed is narrow or weak AI. A weak AI is simply one work or is built for **one** specific purpose. No matter how much the AI develops, if we change fields and place them in differing situations, they would not be able to apply the knowledge they possess to adapt in the situation as easily as humans. Therefore, while AI can possess the qualities of humans and emulate them, they are not human per se nor can they be considered as a potential replacement for humans.

Human and Artificial Intelligence

The entire debate surrounding the human-AI dynamics has developed recently due to the popularisation of technology in

general. Today, most of us have or wish to possess a smartphone. It is interesting that most of us don't realise that the phone becomes "smart" due to the components of AI which are programmed into it. Essentially, it gives the various applications the power to interact not only with itself and the user but also with one another. The applications observe the preferences of the user and offer them items similar to one often used by them. We interact with this form of AI almost on a daily basis without actually realising it.

The relationship between an average human and AI is almost inseparable. But we must proceed with the caveat that they are not same. In this age of plasticity, as identified by the French writer Jacques Ellul in his book "The Technological Society," it is deemed necessary by the majority of the human folk to draw the distinction between the AI and themselves. There is a need amongst the majority to showcase that while an AI is designed to emulate humans, it is not human.

The Definition by Distinction

While it is human tendency to identify and attribute characteristics to their kind, there is also a tendency to exclude individuals or groups and communities from their definitions. It is imperative to understand this concept of differentiating "us" and "them," to understand the role of AI in the lives of humans. At varied points in history, humans have adopted a negative definition of "us." For instance up until the 19th century, there was a culture to identify the women in society as property of men and thus, not significant enough to be identified as "human" in their own right. The tendency to own people as slaves only due to a difference in place of origin and their skin colour also created a layer of distinction and differentiation in human.

In the present time and age, there is a need to exclude Artificial Intelligence from the definition of humans, to define attributes of human itself.

Analysing the above facts we might need to rethink whether there is much of humanity left in humans themselves. to concretely separate them from their machine counterparts. For instance, in the home for the elderly in the United States, there are bots deployed who not only interact with the elderly but also serve and please them. Elderly who have been cast aside by their own for varied reasons, are looked after by machines who supposedly lack emotional quotient. Most elderly, feel more comfortable with these machines than with their own kind, so while we remain human, the ability to be humane must be analysed.

Role of Human in the Age of Artificial Intelligence

Despite having evolved through various stages, humans never felt the need to define what does it actually mean to be human? Is it just our physical attributes which segregate us or do humans have more to them than just biology? It is imperative to understand human and humanity to comprehend the need or the ability to stay human in the age of artificial intelligence.

The definition of the human starts out as one purely biological. The term human comes from the Latin term *humanus* which means “man or human.” Most definitions of human define a human as having certain characteristics belonging to mammals of the humankind. It is these characteristics that differentiate humans from machines and machine learning in the present age.

Immanuel Kant, philosopher and writer, identified one of the major attributes of humans to be – rationality. The ability of being rational is to differentiate between “what ought to be?” and “what it is?.” Thereby, humans possess not just the ability to think but to think at various levels. For Viktor Frankl, the identity of a human includes the ability to assign “meaning” and the only way humans move forward is by assigning meaning to events in time. Humans emphasize on the need for meaning to create a purpose in life. Without purpose, according to Frankl humans find it difficult to survive.

The paper analyses the role of AI in the increasingly technological world while simultaneously highlighting the relation and power dynamics shared between the Human and the Machine. A special focus is aimed at understanding the vulnerable and insecure position of humans and human relations in the “age of plasticity.”

Machines decidedly do not fit in either of these definitions. Machines do only what they are programmed to do. They lack the ability to assign meaning to events as humans do. To humans, an object has not just physical meaning but the emotional meaning attached to it but machine lack the ability to emote in the same manner. They do, however, have a purpose but it is not something that they discover but are programmed to do. They do not have to think in multiple layers or rather they unable to. While there are scientists working on the ability to develop rationality amongst the machines, they have little to no success. The machines unlike humans, accept and observe everything on the nominal value. They utilise data available to them or collected by them to learn and unlearn behaviour.

Humans, on the other hand, are complex creatures who are governed with an inherent sense of morality. Morality in its most basic sense would mean the ability to differentiate between wrong and right. For ages now, the most forceful argument against AI is that they lack morality, which for the most part is true. While morality is something that comes naturally to humans, it is difficult for machines to have the same despite being programmed for the same. For machines concepts like right and wrong are ironclad- black and white, their inability to see the grey area in the middle, would prevent them from being human in every right.

These abilities- rationality, morality and the ability to assign meaning to everything that happens, is natural to *Homo sapiens*. While not enough, but this creates a world of difference between a human and a human-machine i.e. artificial intelligence. To summarise, the ability to be connected to meaning, to identify the grey area and to preserve such qualities is essential in a world where being attached to a wire is gaining prevalence. In simple terms being human in the age of AI is the ability to emote and communicate without being pre-programmed to do so.

Conclusion

There is a new need within humans to distinguish themselves from the machine humans due to a fear that they would eventually replace humans and take over human society. While many science fiction movies make it look plausible, the present technology is not to replace humans but essentially to assist them. The present generations of the machine are the new slaves. Most psychologists and scientists explain the power dynamics in simple terms. Never in the history of the world has anyone intended to create something more powerful than themselves. Similarly, the narrow AI which is being developed is not going to replace humans, simply because it lacks the capacity to do so.

The present AI has a lot of flaws but it is a tool in the hands of humans at the end of the day. There is a possibility of evil but there is more potential for good. Whether we like it or not we have entered into the age of AI and not only has AI become more like us but we emulate their characteristics too. Thereby, we are inseparable and highly dependant on AI for everything. Needless to say, this AI shares our fears and our biases as well. When the creator is flawed the creation is equally flawed.

To be human in the age of AI should create a position of responsibility and not that of fear. The ability to make machines think like us is a great power which has to be limited by a keen sense of responsibility. Technology is responsible hands is always a boon. As Charles Dickens remarks, “It was the best of times, it was the worst of times,” and it is more true for AI than we can perceive. The positive use of AI envisages great possibilities of development and in the same manner AI is a weapon for mass destruction. The choice then rests in the hands of the creator and his capacity to be humane.

References

- Ellul, J. (1955). *The Technological Society*. France.
- Isofocus. (2019, November 11). *To Eticize or not to Ethicize*. Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/news/ref2454.html>
- John McCarthy, M. L. (1955). *A Proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Conference*.
- Patrick Lin, K. A. (2011, January 19). *Robot ethics: Mapping the issues for a mechanized world*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0004370211000178>
- PwC. (2015). *What’s the real value of AI for your business and how can you capitalise?* Retrieved from PwC: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/analytics/assets/pwc-ai-analysis-sizing-the-prize-report.pdf>

- Smith, D. L. (2012, May 16). *What Does It Mean to Be Human?*
Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/philosophy-dispatches/201205/what-does-it-mean-be-human>
- Spector, L. (2006, November 07). *Evolution of Artificial Intelligence.*
Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S000437020600>
- Tegmark, M. (2017). *Life 3.0.* United States: Knopf.
- Winograd, T. (n.d.). *Shifting viewpoints: Artificial intelligence and.*
Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0004370206000920>
- Zawacki-Richter, O. (2019). *Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators?* Retrieved from <https://educationaltechnologyjournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>

Diksha Garg is a student of the St. Joseph's College of Law, Bangalore. She has been born and brought up in the study and is in the penultimate year of completion of the 5-year B.A.LLB course. She has an interest in varied and innovative areas of law, and aims to understand the role of law in a world increasingly marred with technology. She has a great interest in writing and has pursued the same by means of various internships and collaborations. Email: dikshagarg2508@gmail.com

Received April 13, 2020; Accepted May 7, 2020; Words: 2870

© by the authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).